

cemented tank. A water depth of 50 cm above the seedling level and a water temperature of 30 °C were maintained for 12 d. Recovery score was measured 7 d after submergence (1-5, tolerant; >5-9, susceptible).

ANOVA revealed significant differences among the populations in reaction to submergence.

Submergence scores in the F₁s of four crosses-FR43B(T)/IR42(S), FR43B(T)/Pankaj(S), Rahaspanjar(T)/IR42(S), and Rahaspanjar(T)/

Pankaj(S)-tended toward those of the tolerant parents.

In the F₂ generation, the segregation ratio was 9:7 (T:S) (see table). This ratio indicated that submergence tolerance can be explained by the complementary action of at least two genes. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Performance of different rice lines in Zn-deficient soil

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Ten rice lines with different responses to Zn deficiency were grown in a Zn-deficient soil with 0 (Zn0) or 10 (Zn10) mg Zn kg⁻¹ soil. The soil was a fine montmorillonitic calcareous Typic Hydraquent from Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines (DTPA-extractable Zn 0.04 mg kg⁻¹, pH 7.8). Portions (3 kg) of the

soil were placed in plastic pots and flooded with water for 3 wk. Pre-germinated seeds were then sown and the plants were grown for 3 wk in a glasshouse under typical humid tropical wet-season conditions. The following measurements were made: Zn deficiency score by the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice*, number of leaves with Zn deficiency symptoms, number of tillers, plant height, shoot dry weight, and shoot Zn content.

Nine indices of performance were calculated from the results and ranked (Table 1). These indices are all quantitative and Zn-specific, and could therefore be used for quantitative trait loci (QTL) analysis. The indices were used to distinguish different performance characteristics (Table 2).

Results showed that lines IR26, IR58, CSR10, and IR65 were intolerant of Zn deficiency, with IR26, CSR10, and IR65 tending to accumulate Zn without an increase in growth. Lines IR8192, Madhukar, FR13A, Ketumbar, and to a

Table 1. Performance indices for growth under Zn deficiency.

Performance index	Scoring	Ranking ^a											
		IR26	IR58	IR65	CSR10	Ketumbar	KDML 105	IR9764	Mahsuri	FR 13 A	IR8192	Kuatik Putih	Madhukar
Visual score in Zn0	a: best, d: worst	d	c	b	b	a	c	a	c	a	a	c	a
Number of leaves with deficiency symptoms in Zn0	a: least, d: most	d	c	b	b	b	c	a	d	d	a	d	d
Shoot dry wt/shoot Zn concentration in Zn0	a: highest, c: lowest	c	b	c	b	b	b	b	c	a	a	c	b
Shoot dry wt/ quantity of Zn in shoot in Zn0	a: highest, g: lowest	f	b	g	e	b	b	c	f	b	a	d	c
Shoot Zn concentration in Zn0	a: highest, e: lowest	a	e	a	b	e	c	b	a	e	e	b	d
Quantity of Zn in shoot in Zn0	a: highest, c: lowest	c	c	c	c	c	b	b	c	a	a	c	a
Av % growth (dry wt, tiller no.) reduction	a: least, d: most	c	d	d	c	b	b	b	b	b	a	a	a
(Dry wt Zn0/dry wt Zn10)%	a: highest, d: lowest	c	c	b	d	c	a	b	d	a	a	d	a
(Dry wt Zn10 - dry wt Zn0)/quantity of Zn supplied	a: highest, g: lowest	f	e	g	b	d	f	c	a	b	a	b	b

^aThe same letters in a row indicate that rankings are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ by Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 2. Performance characteristics based on indices in Table 1.

Characteristic	Index rankings required	IR26	IR58	IR65	CSR10	Ketumbar	KDML 105	IR9764	Mahsuri	FR13A	IR8192	Kuatik Putih	Madhukar
Tolerance deficiency	Low 1, 2, 7	L ^a	L	ML	ML	H	MH	H	MH	MH	H	MH	H
Internal efficiency (transport and use within plant)	High 3, 4, 6; low 5	-	-	-	-	H	M	L	L	H	H	L	H
External efficiency (mobilization in rhizosphere, absorption)	Low 3, 4, 6; high 5	-	-	-	-	L	M	H	H	L	L	H	L
Responsiveness	High 8, 9	L	M	L	MH	M	L	M	MH	H	HH	MH	H
High accumulation (high shoot Zn with poor growth)	High 5, low 6	H	L	H	H	L	M	H	H	L	L	H	L
Low accumulation (low shoot Zn with good growth)	Low 5, high 6	L	MH	L	L	M	M	ML	L	HH	HH	L	H

^aH = high, M = moderate, L = low.

lesser extent, KDML 105 were efficient in internal transport and use of Zn; IR9764, Mahsuri, Kuantik Putih, and to a lesser extent, KDML 105 were efficient in Zn acquisition from the soil. Lines IR8192, FR13A, and Madhukar were responsive to Zn addition as well as efficient in internal use. ■

Genetic variability and path analysis in rice grown in saline soil

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Our study aimed to examine genetic variability, heritability, and correlation coefficients among different characters when rice varieties were grown under saline conditions. We estimated the genetic parameters of seven quantitative characters in 20 rice genotypes grown under saline conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design and replicated three times during 1995-96 on saline soils (4-5 dS m⁻¹) at the Rice Research Station "Jucarito," Granma Province, Cuba. Hills were spaced 20 × 10 cm, with a single seedling hill⁻¹. Observations were recorded on five randomly selected plants replication⁻¹. The mean, standard deviation, phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), broad-sense heritability (h²), and genetic advance as a percentage of mean (GA%) were calculated for seven traits. Path coefficient analysis was used to partition the genotypic correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects.

Significant differences were observed for all traits, indicating great variability between genotypes. PCV was usually higher than GCV, but the difference was very low, indicating less environmental influence on the expression of different traits. The

higher GCV and PCV for grain yield plant⁻¹, panicle weight, and plant height provided better scope for improvement through selection for saline conditions (Table 1).

A moderate amount of variability (11-12%) was observed for panicles plant⁻¹ and filled grains panicle⁻¹, whereas a low GCV and low GA% were observed for panicle length and 1,000-grain weight. These indicated that the characters were under high environmental influence, and that selection based on these characters would be ineffective under saline conditions.

The high value of GCV, h², and GA% estimated for grain yield plant⁻¹, plant height, and panicle weight indicated the predominance of additive gene action, and that direct phenotypic selection based on these traits would be effective for varietal improvement on saline soils.

Grain yield plant⁻¹ was positively and significantly correlated with panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, 1,000-grain weight, and plant height, but negatively and significantly correlated with panicles plant⁻¹. Panicle length did not show any correlation with yield (Table 2).

The path coefficient analyses also indicated that panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and plant height had the largest direct effect on yield. Thus, these three characters emerged as the main components of rice grain yield under saline conditions. Other characters, such as panicles plant⁻¹, panicle length, and 1,000-grain weight, did not show any direct effect on yield, but they influenced yield via plant height. Panicle weight, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and plant height appeared to be the most reliable indices for selection under Cuba's saline conditions. ■

Table 1. Genetic parameters for seven traits in rice varieties grown in saline soil.

Trait	Mean	Standard deviation	PCV ^a	GCV	h ²	GA%
Plant height (cm)	100.5	1.82	28.18	28.16	90.6	30.2
Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	9.6	0.80	11.52	11.48	94.8	21.4
Panicle length (cm)	24.8	2.24	3.00	2.97	37.2	12.9
Panicle weight (g)	4.3	0.52	22.84	22.80	89.4	22.8
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	92.8	9.60	12.65	12.63	42.5	22.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	29.3	0.80	6.05	6.02	97.0	10.6
Grain yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	12.6	2.62	39.86	39.84	97.2	34.5

^aPCV = phenotypic coefficient of variation, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variation, h² = heritability, GA% = genetic advance as % of mean.

Table 2. Path analysis showing direct and indirect effects on yield.^a

Variable	Plant height	Panicles plant ⁻¹	Panicle length	Panicle weight	Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	1,000-grain weight	Total genotypic correlation with yield
1	0.437	0.145	-0.043	0.078	0.027	-0.088	0.557**
2	-0.148	-0.026	0.040	-0.069	-0.011	0.066	-0.549**
3	0.118	0.107	-0.161	0.055	0.033	-0.082	0.270
4	0.249	0.213	-0.065	1.138	0.017	-0.062	0.691**
5	0.160	0.066	-0.073	0.033	0.575	-0.046	0.875***
6	0.170	0.124	-0.059	0.038	0.015	0.226	0.564**

^aResidual effect = 0.082 direct effects. All others are indirect effects. ** = significant at 5% level, *** = significant at 1% level.